

SATISFACTORY

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DELIVERABLE D6.4 REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES, PUBLIC PARTICIPATION AND AWARENESS

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SATISFACTORY CONSORTIUM

The Satisfactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH ¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
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Main colours

	ORANGE	OCHRE	YELLOW	GREY	BLACK
RGB	246 142 30	255 209 117	255 206 0	88 88 90	0 0 0
HEX	F68E1E	FFD175	FFCE00	58585A	000000

Secondary colours

	ORANGE	DARK BLUE	ORANGE2	BROWN	LIGHT BLUE
RGB	246 142 30	0 124 169	255 159 57	169 93 10	30 188 246
HEX	F68E1E	007CA9	FF9F39	A95D0A	1EBCF6

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
IMS	Intelligent Manufacturing Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PFS	Presentation and Feedback Session
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020).

The report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness (D6.4) summarises the main dissemination and communication activities that have been performed during the first year of the project. This periodic report is yearly updated (M12, M24 and M36). It focuses on the various media, material and networks that have been used or created, and the events that have been attended, with the aim of promoting the project research activities and results, and fostering its exploitation potential.

1. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

1.1 PROJECT LOGO

Sigma Orionis prepared several designs for the SatisFactory logo. The logo was selected by partners on the occasion of the project kick-off meeting on January 22, 2015.

Figure 1 – SatisFactory logo

The project logo was designed to picture the ideas of:

- Attractive place for workers (sunshine colours);
- Re-adaptation of production facilities with human-centred technologies (conventional symbol of factory surrounded by dynamic symbol of human);
- Innovation (yellow colour) and ICT technology (digital-like squares coming out of the factory chimney);
- Knowledge-sharing (circle).

1.2 GRAPHIC CHARTER

The graphical identity derived from the project logo has been developed at M1. It details the use of logotype, colours and fonts to be used by the project. All project materials are developed in line with this graphic charter.

Figure 2 – SatisFactory colours from the graphic charter

<u>Main colours</u>					
	ORANGE	OCHRE	YELLOW	GREY	BLACK
RGB	246 142 30	255 209 117	255 206 0	88 88 90	0 0 0
HEX	F68E1E	FFD175	FFCE00	58585A	000000

<u>Secondary colours</u>					
	ORANGE	DARK BLUE	ORANGE2	BROWN	LIGHT BLUE
RGB	246 142 30	0 124 169	255 159 57	169 93 10	30 188 246
HEX	F68E1E	007CA9	FF9F39	A95D0A	1EBCF6

1.3 PROJECT TEMPLATES

Following the definition of the project visual identity, project templates were developed at M3 to ensure that all documents produced by the project are sharing the same design and remain consistent with the project image during the entire project period. SatisFactory's set of templates includes templates for Project Deliverables, PowerPoint presentations and Newsletters.

Table 1 – Project templates (agenda)

PROJECT TEMPLATES		
SatisFactory's set of templates:	Already done?	Due date
Project deliverables	✓	M3
Project PowerPoint presentations	✓	M3
Newsletters	✓	M6

Figure 3 – Overview of project templates (deliverables and PowerPoint presentation)

2. NETWORK OF INTEREST

- **Contact email**

The contact email info@satisfactory-project.eu was created at M2 and is added to all project communication materials and online tools. This contact email is managed by the dissemination and communication leader (SIGMA).

- **Newsletter audience**

SatisFactory is targeting various stakeholders (mainly from manufacturing and research sectors) through a communication mailing list called “Network of Interest” (NoI). The NoI list will be used when publishing the newsletter and communicating about events. All project partners have access to a shared file to suggest potential members from external organizations. Information on project activities, progress, outcomes and events, will be regularly flowed through newsletters sent from info@satisfactory-project.eu.

At the end of the first year (M12), the Network of interest was composed of 134 people, divided into 3 segments:

- Project partners: 46 members
- Members suggested by partners: 54 members
- Subscribers to the newsletter: 34 members

3 segments	M6	M12
Recommended by partners	30	54
Project partners	46	46
Newsletter subscribers	6	34
Total	82	134

The expected performance is 300 NoI contacts by the end of the project.

3. PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

3.1 REFERENCE PROJECT PRESENTATION

At M3 the project coordinator (CERTH) produced a preliminary PowerPoint presentation to highlight the project's key facts, concept and objectives. Partners can use this reference presentation to introduce the project and its activities when attending events.

3.2 PROJECT FLYER, BROCHURE AND POSTER

A promotional flyer and a poster have been designed at M3. The flyer describes the project's key facts, objectives and expected results so that the general public can quickly understand what the project is about. Two hundred copies of the flyer and ten copies of the poster have been printed and shared among partners in order to be handed out at events. A brochure containing the project results is being at M12 and will be updated at M30 to present the final outcomes of the project.

Table 2 – Project promotional materials

PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS				
	Format	Copies	Due date	Done?
Flyer	15x21	x200	M3	✓
Poster	60x80	x10	M3	✓
Brochure	X	X	M12, M30	M13

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Figure 4 – Project flyer

3.3 VIDEO TRAILER

A short video trailer has been produced at M7 and is available on YouTube. The video aims to inform a wide audience about innovative solutions developed by the project partners in order to create smart and attractive factories. To this end, the video contains:

- Interviews of project partners
- A presentation of the technologies developed all along the project
- Shots from the three pilot plants

Interviews of project partners have been filmed during the 2nd Plenary Meeting, on May 28-29, 2015, in Brussels. Videos are a very effective way to communicate. They can be easily shared on the web, and displayed on wide screens at events. Other videos will be produced in order to promote the project objectives and on-going research activities.

4. PROJECT WEBSITE AND SEO

A project website (<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/>) was created at M3 and is a deliverable (D6.1) due at M6. The SatisFactory website is constantly updated with the latest project news and will be continuously improved all along the project lifetime.

4.1 WEBSITE STRATEGY

The website is a key communication tool to increase the project visibility and the impact towards the industry decision-makers, communities of researchers and the general public. Initially due at M6, online at M3 and constantly updated, the SatisFactory website (D6.1) contains all relevant information about the project and related topics (SatisFactory objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports, analysis, links to related initiatives). The main objective of the website is to spread the project goals and results as widely as possible. SatisFactory's website is released under the Creative Commons (CC) license, a public copyright license. The website development and maintenance is led by SIGMA.

Table 3 – SatisFactory website: key facts

SatisFactory website – Key facts	
Website URL:	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/
Main objective	The project website spreads the project objectives and results as widely as possible
License	Creative Commons license
Target audience	At least 8,000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project

Priority was given to news about the project progress, a presentation of SatisFactory solutions and technologies, and their implementation in the three pilot sites. The template used (Porcelain) is especially adapted to this use and allows highlighting the core messages in a visually appealing slider.

4.2 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The overall structure of the website is the following:

Figure 5 – Website structure

The website homepage was given special care in order to give direct access to a short introduction of the project, and to show the main SatisFactory concepts and link to the website key contents, as shown in “Annex 2 – Project website homepage”.

The website is fully integrated with the project social media, as both tools are complementary for SatisFactory online presence strategy.

4.3 WEBSITE KPIs AND ANALYTICS (M3 TO M12)

Close monitoring based on analytical tools – such as Google Analytics and Google Search Console – and Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) have been used to improve the overall website’s efficiency.

- **Project website ranking on search engines**

Ambitious internal targets have been set in order to foster the challenge of creating an attractive website. The website is expected to rank among the top 10 (from M9 to M12), top 5 (from M12 to M24) and top 3 (from M24 to M36) on Search Engine Results Page (SERP) using the following three predefined key expressions:

- SatisFactory project
- Horizon 2020 satisfaction industry
- satisfaction augmented reality industry

As shown in the following graph, the goal is almost achieved for the first period (M9-M12). Improvements will be made based on these analytics.

Figure 6 – Project website ranking on SERP during the first period (from M9 to M12)

A more detailed list of top research keywords linking to the project website is available in Annex 4.

- **Website visitors (data from Google Analytics)**

Preliminary metrics of the website attendance are shown in “Annex 5 – Website visitors (M3 to M12)”. Further updates and analysis will be provided in each iteration of the D6.4 at M12, M24 and M36.

Table 4 – Website visitors

Website visitors (internal KPI vs. actual)					
KPI	Expected / actual	M6	M12	M24	M36
Number of unique visitors/month	Expected	100	200	250	300
	Actual	745	780	 	
Minimum average visit duration	Expected	3'	3'	3'	3'
	Actual	1'45"	1'36"	 	
Position in SERPs on 3 predefined key expressions	Expected	Among top 10	Among top 5	Top 5	Top 3
	Actual	Top 1 Top 11 Top 16	Top 1 Top 5 Top 7	 	

A constant monitoring, using appropriate tools (web analytics, survey) and performance measurements, will be done, in order to measure the quality and success of SatisFactory communication and dissemination efforts, and to readjust actions whenever required.

5. PROJECT SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

Social media activities contribute to increase the project impact and foster networking & clustering between targeted stakeholders. The project uses social media to share relevant news as widely as possible and engage with identified target groups in Europe and beyond. The project online community development will leverage on interactions with already existing communities, thus legitimating Satisfactory in the field.

Figure 7 – Social media accounts

5.1 TWITTER

A project Twitter account (@SatisfactoryEU) was created at M2 and is fully operational since M4. The project community manager (SIGMA) uses social media dashboard applications (Tweetdeck and Hootsuite) to curate information from influencers and to schedule posts. Twitter analytics tools ensure Social Media Optimisation (SMO).

Table 5 – Twitter analytics

TWITTER ANALYTICS			
	(M6)	Current situation (M12)	Expected impact by the end of the project (M36)

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Twitter followers	149	459	300
Average of tweets posted every week	15	11	> 5

5.2 LINKEDIN

A project LinkedIn account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created at M2 on the basis of a “company page” template, enabling high visibility. LinkedIn is convenient for professional purposes, enabling project partners to add the project LinkedIn webpage to their online LinkedIn CV.

The expected impact is:

- 100 LinkedIn subscribers by the end of the project
- At least 1 LinkedIn post published every two weeks

These goals will be easily reached, with currently 42 LinkedIn subscribers.

5.3 FACEBOOK

A project Facebook account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created at M2 to relays the website news.

Expected impact:

- 100 Facebook likes by the end of the project
- At least 1 post every week

More than 80 people have liked the project Facebook page up to M12.

5.4 YOUTUBE

A project YouTube channel (SatisFactory Project) was created at M2 to upload short videos introducing the project, its partnership, activities, as well as past event trailers. Currently, three videos are online, presenting:

- The SatisFactory video trailer
- The Incident Detection tool, developed by CERTH
- SatisFactory participation to the “Affidabilità e Tecnologie” (A&T) exhibition in Turin, Lingotto Fiere, April 22-23, 2015. This video was created by REGOLA

Expected impact:

- At least 600 video views by the end of the project
- At least 10 videos published during the project

The project video trailer collected more than 470 views on YouTube up to M12.

6. PROJECT PRESS RELEASES AND PUBLICATIONS

6.1 PRESS RELEASES

A first press release was prepared by CERTH at M2 to announce the launch of the project and then sent out to targeted media. A second press release has been prepared by SIGMA at M12 in order to inform the target audience about the project's main achievements with regard to augmented reality for industry. This second press release is expected to be published both on SatisFactory's and AREA's websites (AREA is the Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance). This dissemination is carried out in synergy with all partners, relaying the press release through their networks.

6.2 NEWSLETTER AND EMAIL BLASTS

A newsletter will be issued every six months to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the project news and developments. The newsletter is drafted by SIGMA and contains major announcements related to project activities (report available, event announced, etc.). It circulates on partner's networks. A professional emailing solution (Mailchimp) is used to ensure the best delivery performance.

The first newsletter was published at M6 (see "Annex 2: Project newsletter") and disseminated to 103 subscribers. In particular, the video link obtained a high click rate (20% of the clicks). Another newsletter will be released at M13.

6.3 RESEARCH PAPERS AND ARTICLES

Project partners commit to publish technical articles, papers and reports presenting project activities and results in highly reputed journals and magazines to spread knowledge among the identified manufacturing and research target groups and ensure sustainable exploitation of project outcomes.

6.4 PUBLIC DELIVERABLES

A major expression of external dissemination is the production of deliverables. Over the entire project duration, the SatisFactory project consortium will produce 33 official deliverables. 21 of them will be made publicly available in the project website resources area in order to spread the project excellence and disseminate knowledge as widely as possible.

6.5 FOLLOW-UP TABLES OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Shared sheets were created by SIGMA at the beginning of the project to easily share information among partners on dissemination and communication activities.

Four lists are available:

1. Follow-up list of partners' attendance to external events promoting SatisFactory, and their contribution: exhibition booth, distribution of flyers, etc.
2. Dissemination channels (newspapers, websites, social medias).
3. Network of interest (NoI): identified stakeholders interested by the SatisFactory project. This list will be used for disseminating project newsletters and promoting project events.
4. Published news and press releases about SatisFactory.

7. EVENTS AND NETWORKING

7.1 PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK SESSIONS (PFS)

- **Concept of the PFSs**

Every year, the project will organize a Presentation and Feedback Session (PFS) by taking part to a major forum or trade show in the field of smart manufacturing to maximize the impact on potential clients. These conferences organised by the consortium will facilitate dissemination of the project results to manufacturing and research groups and represent an opportunity to receive valuable feedback from those stakeholders.

- **First PFS: Hannover Messe 2016, 25-29 April 2016**

For its first Presentation and Feedback Session, SatisFactory applied to Hannover Messe 2016, more precisely in the Research and Technology trade fair, which will be held on 25-29 April 2016 (for more details see "Annex 1: Technology demonstration at Hannover Messe"). Three project partners (SIGMA, CERTH and GlassUp) are managing the organisation of SatisFactory participation to Hannover Messe, wishing to set up an exhibition booth.

7.2 CONTRIBUTIONS TO EXTERNAL EVENTS

SatisFactory's contribution to related external events – dealing, for example, with manufacturing, ICT, augmented reality, and others research and innovation area – will favour intense exchange of information and know-how with relevant target groups. The expected performance is a contribution to 10 external events.

For example, SatisFactory participated in the “Affidabilità e Tecnologie” (A&T) exhibition in Turin, Lingotto Fiere, April 22-23, 2015. SatisFactory booth was supported by REGOLA and COMAU, who also created a promotional video of the event.

Figure 8 – SatisFactory participation at the A&T exhibition, Turin, April 2015

PROMOTING SATISFACTORY IN EXTERNAL EVENTS				
Event name	Partners	Contribution	Date	Place
AT event	REGOLA & COMAU	Attendance; Promoting SatisFactory; Distribution of flyers; Videoclip made	22 – 23 April 2015	Turin
"FoF Impact" workshop, EC	CERTH	Project Coordinator, Mr Tzouvaras : attendance	29 – 30 April 2015	Brussels
Technology Forum	ATLANTIS	Attendance	8 May 2015	Thessaloniki
NANOTECHNOLOGY Matchmaking (B2B) Event	ATLANTIS	Attendance at B2B	8 July 2015	Thessaloniki
ICT2015	CERTH & SIGMA	Attendance; Distribution of flyers	20 – 22 July 2015	Lisbon
Wearable Tech Torino	ISMB	Booth (presenting the UWB-based wearable device)	20 – 21 November 2015	Turin

SatisFactory intends to participate in EuroMaintenance 2016 – a worldwide reference event on industrial maintenance – which will be held on May 30-June 1, in Athens. To this end,

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ATLANTIS, REGOLA and CERTH have submitted an abstract on “Novel tools and approaches for remote maintenance activities”.

7.3 END-USERS TRAINING SESSIONS

A series of (at least 3) Virtual Reality enabled workers training to SatisFactory solution will be held towards the end of the project in cooperation with key stakeholder groups. The (one day) training sessions will ensure the deployment and scaling up of the developed solutions in other factories than the project demonstration sites. These sessions will also enable new users to experiment the solutions and to provide their feedback and eventually will allow to fine-tune the solutions and to prepare their commercialisation.

7.4 INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION - SYNERGIES WITH RELATED ON-GOING INITIATIVES

Synergies and cross promotion with related projects is sought to help spreading the word about the project latest activities, achievements and upcoming events.

International networking activities include organizations from other Factories of the Future projects, through the **European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)**. In particular, common use cases and application scenarios have been identified in partnership with the **Fact4Workers** project. SatisFactory is registered in EFFRA’s database.

The SatisFactory consortium is also liaising with the **Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS)** thanks to partners’ (EPFL and Fraunhofer FIT) business and research networks.

Lastly, SatisFactory is in touch the **Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance (AREA)** – an U.S non-profit organisation dedicated to widespread adoption of interoperable AR-enabled enterprise systems – thanks to GLASSUP. This cooperation takes the form of an exchange of information on AR standards and a two-way dissemination of research results.

CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the D6.4 “Report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness” at M12 of the SatisFactory project. The Report on dissemination activities describes the results of the strategy previously defined in the DCP, and its quantitative (KPI) and qualitative assessment over the first period (M1-M12).

As an Innovation Action (IA), Satisfactory needs concrete market outlets for its products – a set of cutting-edge technologies to be integrated in factory production lines. The dissemination and communication strategy has (1) to allow all relevant stakeholders to be informed about the project activities and outputs, (2) to ensure the highest exploitation potential of SatisFactory products by maximizing information received by potential customers and (3) to support European research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT, thus contributing to enhance industry competitiveness in Europe.

This requires, among other things, creating a corporate identity, publishing promotional materials (such as flyers and press releases), using online communication (project website and social networks), building synergies with related on-going initiatives and participating in high-level events to present the project's progress. The project is making steady progress toward the achievement of these dissemination and communication activities. Almost all the KPI that have been internally set up for the first period (M1-M12) – in order to foster the challenge of realizing an attractive and efficient communication – have been reached.

The D6.4 “Report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness” will be reviewed on an annual basis (M12, M24 and M36). This review will take into account the envisioned KPIs to assess the efficiency and success of such activities. In case the project fails to achieve its targeted objectives, corrective measures will be implemented with the aim of ensuring the project effective dissemination of its results and ultimately the sustainability of project outputs.

ANNEX 1 – TECHNOLOGY DEMONSTRATION PLANNED FOR HANNOVER MESSE 2016

Description of what we wish to show

Two innovative tools: 1) An incident detection tool will show how images from smart depth sensors are analysed, to detect and track workers/visitors, to capture potential events and incidents, and to visualize them on an architectural map. 2) Augmented Reality glasses are proposed as an instructional support tool to on-the-plant manufacturing activities, with overlaid virtual symbology providing real-time instructions for the operators.

Describe the interaction with the exhibition visitors

1) A set of cameras will be installed to a selected area to demonstrate in real-time how the system could detect and track the visitors. The analysis of potential incidents will also be visualized on the system dashboard. 2) The AR glasses prototype will enable real temperature readings from thermocouples within a running system simulation, or/and mechanical parts guided-assembling. Glasses-guided solving of Rubik's cube will also be enabled as a more playful and engaging example.

What is innovative/visionary about the technology or activity we will demonstrate?

1) Event and incident detection is a very complex task, since it requests robust human detection and tracking, and a thorough analysis of human movements. SatisFactory effectively combines highly innovative techniques from various disciplines towards this direction. 2) Augmented-Reality Glasses designed for industry will enable hands-free instruction, guidance and training in manufacturing environments.

What is the expected impact for Europe in terms of re-industrialisation, jobs and societal aspects?

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies and innovative approaches. The project plans to increase the productivity and innovation potential of modern factories, while enhancing the skills of their workers as well as the safety and attractiveness of the industrial workplaces. After a test phase in pilot plants in Italy and Greece, the project is expected to widely disseminate its solutions in European factories.

ANNEX 2 – PROJECT WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

The screenshot shows the homepage of the SatisFactory project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the SatisFactory logo and menu items: OUR SOLUTIONS, SATISFACTORY, PILOT SITES, NEWS AND EVENTS, and CONTACT US. Social media icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube are also present. The main header features a large orange background with the text "SATISFACTION & WORK EXPERIENCE" and the tagline "Making attractive and collaborative workplaces". Below this, the SatisFactory logo is repeated, followed by a paragraph explaining the project's goal: "SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to workers. Solutions - including smart sensors and augmented-reality approaches - will be demonstrated in pilot factories in Italy and Greece." The "Latest News!" section contains three articles: "Video: SatisFactory at A&T Event (Turin)", "SatisFactory's Flyer and Poster are online", and "Günther H. Ottinger - Thoughts on Industry 4.0 Strategy, at Hannover Messe". Each article includes a small image, a title, a brief description, and a "READ MORE" link. At the bottom, a quote from Dr. Dimitrios Tzovaras is displayed: "Manufacturing enterprises need to incorporate human-centric technologies on one hand to increase their competitiveness and on the other to offer a working environment that is knowledge-driven and attractive to employees." The footer includes the European Union logo, a disclaimer about funding from the Horizon 2020 program, and social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, and RSS.

ANNEX 3 – PROJECT NEWSLETTER (BRIEF OVERVIEW)

Creating Attractive and Efficient Workplaces in Smart Factories
with Augmented Reality and other Innovative Tech

In January 2015, a European consortium of researchers and industrialists launched the [SatisFactory project](#), which aims to demonstrate the potential of Industry 4.0 to improve work environment in manufacturing plants.

A set of cutting-edge technologies – including smart sensors and augmented reality – will be introduced in manufacturing facilities in order to make them more productive and more appealing to workers.

Testing Innovative Technologies in Industrial Pilot Sites

SatisFactory technologies will be deployed in three industrial sites in Greece and Italy

Cornau S.p.A

CERTH / CPERI

Systems Sunlight S.A.

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ANNEX 4 – TOP RESEARCH KEYWORDS LINKING TO THE PROJECT WEBSITE (GOOGLE SEARCH CONSOLE)

Nombre total de clics	Position moy.
546	16,0

	Requêtes	Clics ▼	Position
1	industry 4.0 pdf	35	8,5 >>
2	industry 4.0	11	33,5 >>
3	satisfactory project	9	1,0 >>
4	fof 2016	5	4,7 >>
5	industry 4.0 european commission	4	4,9 >>
6	eu industry 4.0	4	3,9 >>
7	factory of the future horizon 2020	3	5,7 >>
8	h2020 fof 2016	3	5,4 >>
9	augmented reality automotive industry	2	10,0 >>
10	industry 4.0 uk	2	20,5 >>
11	what is industry 4.0	2	20,5 >>
12	industries 4.0	2	49,1 >>
13	horizon 2020 fof	2	7,1 >>
14	horizon 2020 factories of the future	2	6,1 >>

ANNEX 5 – WEBSITE VISITORS (M3 TO M12)

- Website visitors: source channels

		Acquisition		
		Sessions ↓	% New Sessions ↓	New Users ↓
		6,306	74.67%	4,709
1	Referral	2,220		
2	Direct	2,084		
3	Organic Search	1,515		
4	Social	451		
5	Email	36		

Top Channels

SATISFACTORY

- Website visitors: source countries (M3 to M12)

Sessions by Country

United States (not set) France Greece Italy
Germany Autres

- Website visitors: new users

- New Users

ANNEX 6 – SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS (M3 TO M12)

- Twitter analytics

- YouTube analytics

- **LinkedIn analytics**

- **Facebook analytics**

ANNEX 7 – YOUTUBE VIDEOS

- YouTube video: Incident Detection by CERTH

- YouTube video: SatisFactory Video Trailer

